

The Role of Context in Revealing the Meaning of the Utterance

Fayzullayev Dilshod, master's department graduator Uzbekistan State University of
World Languages

Djabbrova Kizlarxon Abdulakhatovna, Senior teacher, Uzbekistan State University of
World Languages

ABSTRACT

This article deals with exploring the link between meaning and context in the stories in the linguistic context. In language, meaning and context are closely connected with each other, as a result of which the authors express the utterance of their heroes successfully. Simultaneously, the readers will be able to catch the true meaning of the information they are reading. This article shows that context considers a major factor at addressing meaning and meaning occupies an integral role at establishing context.

Keywords: Meaning, Context, Utterance, Dialogues, Communication.

INTRODUCTION

Meaning can be investigated by different branches of linguistics. Meaning is the basement of language, since the aim of communication is mainly to convey meaning. Abdullah Soliman Nouraldeen stated in his article "Meaning is more than a definition in a dictionary; it is also found in a context. Meaning and context are interdependent, i.e., meaning cannot be communicated without context, and context cannot be established without meaning¹. The meaning of a word can be inferred by context. The meaning is revealed in most cases in dialogues in the stories, which reflect different types of contexts that relate to meaning, such as nonlinguistic or situational contexts. The word 'context' is used by different authors and communities for different but often interrelated and dependent notions. Linguists often refer to the context of phrase or word as the text that surrounds it. Another everyday usage of 'context'

¹ British Journal of English Linguistics Vol.3, No.2, pp.13-17, May 2015 Published by European Centre for Research Training and Development UK (www.eajournals.org) 13 Meaning and Context-Three Different Perspectives. Abdullah Soliman Nouraldeen

refers to a section of the real world in which some events or the discourse takes place, and is often intertwined and confused with another meaning, namely knowledge about the same thing.

MATERIALS AND ANALYSIS

There are three key components that speakers must include when communicating: syntax, vocabulary and semantics (Gärdenfors, 1993, p. 285). Words that coincide in the same context have a syntactic and semantic relationship (Cheung & Fung, 2004, p. 254). Successful communication is assured when the hearer properly interprets two contexts: the discourse context, i.e., the information contained in the words, and the physical-social context, i.e., the hearer's knowledge of the speaker, environment, and circumstances (Kreidler, 1998, p. 23). For example: In the story "Long walk to forever" by Kurt Vonnegut

.....Can- can you come to the wedding, Newt?" she said. "That I doubt," he said. "Your furlough isn't long enough?" she said. "Furlough?" said Newt. He was studying a two-page ad for flat silver. "I'm not on furlough," he said. "Oh?" she said. "I'm what they call AWOL," said Newt. "Oh, Newt! You're not!" she said. "Sure I am," he said, still looking at the magazine. "Why, Newt?" she said. "I had to find out what your silver pattern is," he said. He read names of silver patterns from the magazine. "Albamarle? Heather?" he said. "Legend? Rambler Rose?" He looked up, smiled. "I plan to give you and your husband a spoon," he said. "Newt, Newt, tell me really," she said. "I want to go for a walk," he said.

In this extract we find out that Catherine is repeating the modal verb "can" and is somehow shy to invite Newt to her wedding and unwillingly saying about wedding as she herself is in doubt about her true love to her engaged person or future husband. Simultaneously, Newt also is not taking the side of this wedding, because he loves Catherine. The words "still looking at the magazine" expresses that Newt is shy person and cannot look at the girl's eyes, but anyway he keeps inviting her go out with him, standing rigidly. The circumstances are "the time and place, the people involved, their background, their relationship to one another, and what they know about one another. Here several language means (grammatical structures, punctuation, lexical and stylistic means, modal words) come to help to reveal the meaning of the utterance. Another example: In the story "Long walk to forever" by Kurt Vonnegut

... Catharine came out from under her tree, knelt by Newt. "Newt?" she said. "H'm?" he said. "Late," she said. "Hello, Catharine," he said. "Hello, Newt," she said. "I love you." "I

know," she said. "Too late," he said. "Too late," she said. He stood, stretched groaningly. "A very nice walk," he said. "I thought so," she said. "Part company here?" he said. "Where will you go?" she said. "Hitch into town, turn myself in," he said. "Good luck," she said. "You, too," he said. "Marry me, Catharine?" "No," she said.

In the conversation between Newt and Catherine we see different grammatical structures and stylistic means which have great role in revealing the meaning of the heroes' situation and their feelings. Short sentences, elliptical sentences, short answers and the use of the word "Late" repeatedly, but in different meanings indicate us that the heroes have some love affair and they have to solve it. Here the girl is engaged with another person and Newt came before her wedding to confess his love. It is too late to confess his love just before her wedding. The girl is feeling resentful because she also loved Newt, but she agreed to go for Henry Stewart. Her situation is revealed by her short and abrupt answers. At the same time Newt's conversation shows his feeling sorry to come late, but anyway he came and confessed love before the wedding.

He smiled, stared at her hard for a moment, then walked away quickly. Catharine watched him grow smaller in the long perspective of shadows and trees, knew that if he stopped and turned now, if he called to her, she would run to him. She would have no choice. Newt did stop. He did turn. He did call. "Catharine," he called. She ran to him, put her arms around him, could not speak.

In this context we see Newt's confidence in himself after taking the girl out. In the form of conditional sentences the girl's inner love feelings became stronger. Also the use of emotional "did" in Newt's actions points out Newt's diligence and achievement to his love by any means.

DISCUSSIONS

Many dictionaries were used to determine the definition of context, and it was discovered that context was connected to meaning. A context is any area of meaning. Context both influences and is influenced by a sentence's meaning (Christiansen & Dahl, 2005, p. 97). Communication meaning is significantly influenced by context. Therefore, communication cannot be accomplished solely by individual words and sentences. In communication, the context-provided information and the linguistic utterance can interchange information; the more context-provided information there is the less information is needed in the speech. Thus, meaning is created simultaneously by information from context and word meaning. In

conclusion, focusing on words alone can result in ambiguity, while context can give important information to pinpoint the precise meaning. Signs are any formal item that conveys meaning, especially a conventional piece of a system (Kreidler, 1998, p. 303) Conventional signs encountered during every-day life can have multiple context-dependent meanings. For example, the whistle of a policeman directing traffic, the whistle of a hotel doorman calling a taxi, and the whistle of the referee in a soccer game may all sound exactly the same; however, different contexts allow a listener to distinguish between possible meanings (Kreidler, 1998, pp. 21-22). The meaning of an utterance requires a context: The role of context ranges from disambiguating ambiguous expressions as in we just got to the bank in time, through identification of referents (who is he, where is there, in time for what, in he didn't get there in time), walking ' between the lines messages.... (Cruse, 2004, p. 13) Two expressions can have the same or different normality, or meaning. An example of two words with the same normality is pullover and sweater. Dog and cat are examples of two words that have different normalities; 'our cat has had kittens' is more normal than 'our dog has had kittens'. This concept is referred to as "relative normality" and is an example of a contextual approach to meaning (Cruse, 2004, p. 41). Knowing the goal of a context permits an appropriate interpretation of a text.

General objective contexts appear as true statements, such as scientific facts. They are usually found in documents such as scientific papers and news articles. Subjective contexts include feelings, beliefs, and opinions. Probability contexts are comprehended in human inference and as a consequence of human languages. The role of context in the adequacy of the perception of foreign language speech was convincingly shown in previous studies on the perception of authentic speech discourse complicated by culturally marked vocabulary [1-3]. It is shown that due to the connection of contextual factors, the recipient of the discourse to the system of processing incoming information at the level of the language code acquires additional knowledge about a specific communicative situation, which expands the linguistic information that enters the brain directly during perception, involving cognitive processes of processing the entire complex of incoming information [4]. . In addition, the presentation of authentic statements in a situational context contributes to the optimization of the processes of analysis and synthesis of all the properties of a word as a material language tool and its environment, which make up the actual situational context.

Language phenomena are considered in the unity of the cognitive and communicative functions performed, as well as in conjunction with the human factor, which manifests itself in the personal context of communication. Foreign language colloquial discourse can be presented and interpreted in the form of various models depending on the functioning of the cognitive mechanism of information perception and transmission.

The important role of the context can be extrapolated to the study of the adequacy of the perception of the communicant's direct speech and its transmission through indirect speech to a third person, when the addresser and the addressee are representatives of different linguistic cultures. This is explained by the fact that the basis of the process of such indirect communication is certain intentions of the speaker in the context of a specific communicative situation, determined by its socio-cultural background and features of communicative implementation. Time and space contexts occur in human reasoning and language. Domain contexts concern restrictions regarding the domain of applicability of a statement. Necessity contexts specify necessary conditions for something to happen, e.g., the verb "must". Planning contexts involve information about someone's plans or wishes. When several contexts of different types overlap or coincide, richness in information rather than conflict is achieved.

CONCLUSION

Meaning and context are interrelated in a variety of situations. Successful communication cannot be achieved without the integration of meaning and context. Teachers need to combine meaning and context to arrive at a full command of different language skills. To provide an accurate translation, translators and interpreters must carefully consider contexts. Inference, ambiguity and conventional signs are important factors when seeking to understand meaning and context. It is clear that meaning cannot be understood without context. Relative normality is a semantic concept that is related to meaning and context. A variety of aspects of contexts lead to proper interpretation or understanding of the meaning of a text.

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